

Optical design of a mode cleaner for a small-scale suspended interferometer for Quantum Noise reduction in gravitational wave detectors

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Abstract

A mode cleaner optical cavity is a resonator that can be tuned to transmit a desired transverse mode present in the incoming beam, suppressing all the others. We present the optical design of a suited input mode cleaner for a small-scale Michelson interferometer, called SIPS (Suspended Interferometer for Ponderomotive Squeezing). The physical goal is to feed SIPS with a beam with a Gaussian profile, which also ensures a highly focused beam along the propagation axis. The SIPS mode cleaner has been designed to have a maximum circulating power of 130 W, and to deliver a transmitted power of at least 2.5 W in input of SIPS interferometer. It guarantees a suppression factor of at least 20 dB for every tested higher order mode. This work is framed within the implementation of a table-top optical experiment to test the broadband Quantum Noise reduction in the SIPS sensitivity curve, via frequency-dependent squeezing achieved by employing Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) quantum entangled states of light.

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Introduction

On 14 September 2015, a century after the birth of General Relativity, all the scientific and technological efforts for the experimental direct detection of gravitational-waves (GWs) found a reward [1]. The instruments that allowed this milestone achievement are the second-generation GW interferometers known as Advanced LIGO [2], during the scientific observing run named O1. Advanced Virgo [3, 4] joined the LIGO network in August 2017, towards the end of the observing run O2. At the time of writing, after the conclusion of the O3 run, 90 GW events have been confirmed [5, 6, 7]. The world-wide network of detectors will see an important extension with KAGRA [8], which will join LIGO and Virgo starting from the next run O4.

Future challenges concern further technological improvements and the extension of the world-wide network of GW detectors. New techniques and strategies should be implemented for reducing any

Figure 1: Conceptual scheme of the optical table-top setup for producing EPR entangled squeezed beams and testing them into SIPS. The subsystem of the laser injection into SIPS is detailed.

source of noise which can hide the GW signals. In particular, at present time, GW detectors are limited by Quantum Noise (QN) in a broad window of their detection band. Frequency-dependent squeezing (FDS) is the most promising strategy for the mitigation of QN along the whole instrumental bandwidth (10 Hz - 10 kHz). Currently, Virgo and LIGO are implementing a FDS setup which consists in a frequency-independent squeezing (FIS) source coupled with a 300 m-long detuned filter cavity [9]. It will produce FDS in reflection from the filter cavity, to be injected into the dark port of the interferometer. This is expected to work starting from the next observing run O4 of the LIGO-Virgo-KAGRA Collaboration, which is planned to begin in the first half of 2023.

Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) conditional squeezing scheme

A more recent proposal for producing FDS consists in employing Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) entangled states of light [10]. A set up for testing EPR squeezed states into a small-scale suspended interferometer called SIPS (Suspended Interferometer for Ponderomotive Squeezing) is under implementation at the EGO (European Gravitational Observatory, near Pisa, Italy) R&D squeezing laboratory [11, 12]. EPR squeezing has been already tested in a single linear cavity [13, 14], but never in a suspended interferometer like SIPS, designed to be radiation-pressure noise limited in the same frequency band of GW detectors [15]. At the time of writing, the optical and mechanical design of the still missing components is nearing completion. The alignment and characterization of the various optical paths is ongoing. Fig. 1 reports a schematic view of the optical scheme of SIPS injection path.

This novel strategy would avoid the presence of the above-mentioned filter cavity in the layout of future GW detectors, achieving a more compact and cheaper setup, and deleting also the optical losses (~ 1 ppm/m) due to the filter cavity itself. Furthermore, an EPR squeezing source ensures more flexibility to adapt squeezed light features to the interferometer optical configuration. Hence, the EPR conditional squeezing configuration is of great importance especially in view of the third generation GW detectors, such as the Einstein Telescope (ET) [16]. On the other hand, the EPR

technique presents the disadvantage of dealing with two vacuum squeezed beams instead of one.

The EPR setup relies on the production of two entangled frequency-independent squeezed vacuum light beams via an Optical Parametric Oscillator (OPO). It is a cavity hosting a non-linear optical crystal, in which squeezing creation mechanisms take place [17]. The OPO is pumped with a slightly detuned second harmonic beam, with angular frequency $\omega_0 + \Delta$, ω_0 being the resonance frequency of the small-scale interferometer. The same frequency shift Δ is then inherited by the two EPR-entangled squeezed vacuum beams provided by the OPO. They are named as *signal* (ω_0) and *idler* ($\omega_0 + \Delta$). The squeezed beams are injected in SIPS through its dark port, and they are finally separated and sent to two similar homodyne detectors. Here, they beat with reference beams (local oscillators, LOs), for the detection of the squeezing level. The idler acquires a frequency dependence by circulating in the interferometer, without using any external filter cavity. This dependence is transferred to the signal via EPR entanglement. All the lasers in the setup are phase-locked between each other with proper feedback loops, in order to stabilize their mutual frequency shift.

A mode cleaner for a stabilized Gaussian beam

The SIPS mode cleaner is a triangular optical resonator placed between the laser source and the input port of the interferometer. A mode cleaner cavity is needed to reflect out all the unwanted transverse modes of oscillation of the electromagnetic field. Indeed, a generic beam transverse amplitude profile can be conveniently expanded in terms of a complete orthonormal set of functions, like e.g. the so-called Hermite-Gauss basis [18]. These TEM_{nm} (Transverse Electro-Magnetic) modes do not resonate all at the same cavity round-trip length L_{rt} . Therefore, a resonator can be tuned in such a way that only one of them is transmitted, suppressing all the others [19]. A mode cleaner is fundamental also for enhancing the spatial stability of the laser beam, because lateral jitter of the beam axis, or beam width fluctuations, can be modeled as contributions of higher order modes (HOMs) to a purely TEM_{00} beam, which is characterized by presenting a Gaussian intensity profile.

Let us consider an ideal monochromatic beam with frequency $\omega = ck$, propagating in an optical resonator along the z -direction of a suited reference frame. In such a case, a TEM_{00} pure beam with integrated total power P presents this transverse intensity profile:

$$I(r) = \frac{2P}{\pi w^2(z)} e^{-2r^2/w^2(z)}, \quad (1)$$

where $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$ is the squared distance from the beam center. Our ideal beam must be purely TEM_{00} and it is steadily centered on the optical path axis.

We chose for our mode cleaner a layout with two identical flat base mirrors, with amplitude reflectivity labeled as r_1 , and a concave end mirror having an amplitude reflectivity r_2 (see fig. 2). Hence, in the approximation $r_1 \simeq r_2 \simeq 1$, the transmission function is:

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{(1 - r_1^2)^2}{(1 - r_1^2 r_2)^2} \left[1 + \left(\frac{2\mathcal{F}}{\pi} \sin \left(\frac{kL_{rt}}{2} \right) \right)^2 \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{F} is the cavity finesse:

Figure 2: SIPS mode cleaner cavity layout. The beam enters the resonator through the input mirror M_{in} , and it is transmitted towards the interferometer through M_{out} . These are identical and flat, whereas the end mirror is curved and presents a different reflectivity.

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{\pi}{2 \arcsin\left(\frac{1-r_1^2 r_2}{2\sqrt{r_1^2 r_2}}\right)} \simeq \frac{\pi\sqrt{r_1^2 r_2}}{1-r_1^2 r_2}. \quad (3)$$

Considering the overall phase of a generic mode, within the paraxial beam approximation¹, the resonance condition reads as:

$$-kL_{rt} + (n+m+1)\Psi(z) = 2p\pi \quad (4)$$

with p integer. The Gouy phase is indicated with $\Psi(z)$ and it is the key term of the above expression, since it is the one sensitive to the order of the considered mode, given by the sum $n+m$ of the tangential and sagittal indexes. It can be written in our case as $\Psi(z) = 2 \arccos(\sqrt{g})$, so it depends upon the g -factor of the cavity, given by its geometrical layout (see eq. 9). Some algebraic manipulations of eq. 4 easily lead to the resonating frequencies expression:

$$\nu_{pnm} = \frac{c}{L_{rt}} \left[p + \frac{(n+m+1)}{\pi} \arccos(\sqrt{g}) \right]. \quad (5)$$

Notice that c/L_{rt} represents the cavity free spectral range (FSR).

Now, an important difference arises if the resonator is made up by an odd number of mirrors, instead of an even one, e.g. a linear Fabry-Pérot cavity. As outlined in [20, 21], TEM_{nm} modes behave differently in a three-mirror resonator, according to their parity. Modes with odd n index are anti-symmetric with respect to the y -axis: $E(x, y) = -E(-x, y)$. At each reflection, the beam reference frame experiences a 180° rotation about the y -axis. Therefore, an odd number of internal reflections brings to destructive interference if the cavity has a length equal to an integer multiple of the light wavelength, i.e. if $L_{rt} = p\lambda$. To make it resonant, the tuning must be $L_{rt} = (p+1/2)\lambda$. Nothing changes for modes with even n index, symmetric with respect to the y -axis: $E(x, y) = E(-x, y)$. This

¹A beam can be regarded as paraxial when the fields amplitude variation in space is much faster along the transverse directions than the propagation axis.

fact partially removes the degeneracy of the higher order modes (HOMs) in the cavity transmission spectrum, since it leads to a modified resonance condition:

$$-kL_{rt} + (n + m + 1)\Psi(z) + \frac{1 - (-1)^n}{2}\pi = 2p\pi. \quad (6)$$

This in turn allows us to find a more general expression for the resonating frequencies:

$$\nu_{pnm} = \frac{c}{L_{rt}} \left[p + \frac{(n + m + 1)}{\pi} \arccos(\sqrt{g}) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1 - (-1)^n}{2} \right]. \quad (7)$$

The partial removal of HOMs degeneracy helps in distributing their power along the available free spectral range, reducing the power fraction of HOMs resonant with the Gaussian TEM₀₀ mode, transmitted by the mode cleaner. Another important reason to choose a triangular layout is related to an easier readout in reflection. With a linear mode cleaner, we would need some optical scheme with retarding plates to distinguish incoming and reflected light through its polarization. Finally, the off-axis reflection avoids any back-reflected beam towards the laser source.

From the cavity transmission function in eq. 2, and the above considerations, we find that if the cavity is put in resonance on the Gaussian mode, the power suppression factor of a generic HOM is:

$$S_{nm} = 1 + \left[\frac{2\mathcal{F}}{\pi} \sin \left((n + m) \arccos(\sqrt{g}) + \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1 - (-1)^n}{2} \right) \right]^2. \quad (8)$$

Preliminary tests

Our analysis was guided by some requirements to be fulfilled by the final candidate. The design process consisted in two main steps. First of all, it had been necessary to find ranges of interest of the physical parameters. A configuration is individuated by its round-trip length L_{rt} , the radius of curvature (RoC) of its end mirror R_c , the angle of incidence on the end mirror itself θ , and the reflectivities of the coatings r_1 and r_2 . The main necessary conditions that were imposed at this stage concern the optical stability, a low beam astigmatism, and a proper amount of transmitted power. L_{rt} and θ were further limited by constrains of more practical origin, due to the space available for the base mirrors to be installed, and also to the maximum space that the cavity can occupy within the EPR table-top setup.

Optical stability The combination of physical parameters must produce a stable mode cleaner resonator in any case. In principle, due to the different propagation along tangential and sagittal planes, different stability conditions hold for these planes. Nevertheless, since θ is expected to be small, it has been neglected at this first stage. Therefore, a linear hemi-concave cavity with a length $L = L_{rt}/2$ is considered for this test. We are then allowed to use the cavity g-factor formalism. It is defined as the product of the g-factors of the single mirrors:

$$g = g_1 g_2 = 1 - \frac{L}{R_c} \quad (9)$$

where $g_1 = 1$ due to the base mirrors flatness. The stability condition is $0 \leq g \leq 1$, and this is simply expressed as $0 \leq L/R_c \leq 1$.

Figure 3: Stability evaluation test. The dashed red line marks the limit before instability is reached, and the area marked in red is the one approaching instability.

The intervals chosen for L and R_c are limited by several reasons. The former has been varied within the interval $L \in [100; 400]$ mm. A too low L is impossible for geometrical reasons, whereas the available space on the bench imposes an upper limit on the cavity length. Concerning the end mirror RoC, reasonable values are $R_c \in [0.20; 4.00]$ m. The lower limit is given by the constrain about the Gouy phase shift difference between tangential and sagittal planes (see below), and a too high RoC is precursor of an unstable configuration.

Fig. 3 reports the graphical result of the analysis carried out for optical stability. It is not possible to exclude any of the tested values since all the curves fall in the white area of the plot, safely far from instability. However, some configurations approach instability ($g > 0.9$) and these should be avoided.

Beam astigmatism The main issue related to the triangular shape of the mode cleaner is due to astigmatism acquired by the propagating beam. It is originated by the non-normal reflection that occurs on the end mirror. Since the Gouy phase accumulated with a cavity round-trip depends upon the g-factor (see previous section), and this differs between tangential and sagittal planes, a mutual phase lag in the beam components arises. Hence, in principle two different spectra could be produced, one for each component. This is avoided if the phase shift remains much lower than the cavity linewidth:

$$\left| \arccos\left(\sqrt{g^{tan}}\right) - \arccos\left(\sqrt{g^{sag}}\right) \right| \ll \frac{\pi}{2\mathcal{F}} \quad (10)$$

where the g-factors have to be re-defined with respect to eq. 9:

$$g^{tan} = 1 - \frac{L}{R_c \cos \theta} \quad g^{sag} = 1 - \frac{L \cos \theta}{R_c}. \quad (11)$$

As it can be understood from the previous formulae, the driving parameter of this test is the angle θ .

Figure 4: Gouy phase shift for two different values of θ . If $\theta = 10^\circ$ the more strict threshold is overcome in many cases, whereas for $\theta = 5^\circ$ it is satisfied almost in all the configurations. The RoC also plays a role: imposing a lower bound on it is necessary to have proper configurations.

This emerges even clearer in the plots in fig. 4, obtained computing the Gouy phase shift on the same configurations of the stability test. The incidence angle has been fixed to be $\theta = 10^\circ$ and $\theta = 5^\circ$. For this simulation, it is also necessary to put realistic thresholds on the maximum allowed phase shift, and this involves the cavity finesse. A conservative choice at this stage is to consider, as minimum and maximum values, the finesse values resulting from a linear resonator having $R_1 = R_2 = 0.95$ and $R_1 = R_2 = 0.99$. These are respectively $\mathcal{F} = 61.23$ and $\mathcal{F} = 312.58$. A higher finesse produces narrower lines, so it is easier that the Gouy phase shift overcomes the allowed linewidth. Fig. 4 shows that with $\theta = 10^\circ$, we can be not safe in a quite large number of configurations. On the other hand, $\theta = 5^\circ$ guarantees that almost all the configurations produce a Gouy phase shift even under the more strict threshold, obtained with a very high value of finesse for our applications (see below). In other words, the linewidth should be more permissive than the one considered in this test. We then limited the incidence angle to be $\theta \leq 5^\circ$. This test allowed also to restrict a little the range of interest concerning the RoC. The Gouy phase shift diverges for small RoC values, so a good choice can be to impose $R_c \geq 0.6$ m.

Finesse The mode cleaner finesse is defined in eq. 3, and it basically quantifies the cavity linewidth. Moreover, the power gain factor of a resonator can be approximated as $G \simeq 2\mathcal{F}/\pi$ with highly reflective mirrors. Hence, a larger finesse value brings more circulating and transmitted power, and narrower transmission lines, improving the HOMs suppression (see eq. 8).

A trade-off choice is needed. On one hand, SIPS requires by design an input power of 2.5 W [15], and a little more power is requested for cavity control tasks. $\mathcal{F} \approx 60$ is the lowest possible value that can provide such value of output power. On the other hand, a too high finesse would bring to a more difficult control and locking of the cavity via the Pound-Drever-Hall method [22], and the circulating power has to be the lowest possible in order not to stress the coatings, and to keep their production costs low. We imposed $P_{in} = 4$ W as mode cleaner input power, due to the power availability of the laser source. Given this value, a finesse $\mathcal{F} \approx 110$ still ensures a suitable input power to SIPS.

Figure 5: Cavity finesse for linear (shaded lines) and triangular (solid lines) configurations. All the lines cross the blue area of proper values of \mathcal{F} . In order to have values of \mathcal{F} analogous to its linear equivalent, a triangular resonator requires higher values of R_1 and R_2 .

A graphical analysis has been set up and it is shown in fig. 5. Now, using the linear equivalent of a triangular cavity does not represent a truthful test. Indeed, the finesse depends upon the fraction of left power after a round-trip in the cavity, and losses are stronger with three internal reflections. Conservative ranges of variation for the IMC power reflectivities were set up as $R_1 \in [0.95; 0.98]$ and $R_2 \in [0.970; 0.999]$. The base mirrors should have lower reflectivity than the end mirror $R_1 \leq R_2$, to avoid wasting power from the top of the cavity. Ideally, R_2 should be as close as possible to the unitary value, but highly reflective coatings are more expensive.

Best candidate selection

The study illustrated in the previous section made possible to reduce the considered intervals in the parameters' space. Then, all the possible configurations within these restricted intervals have been simulated, by examining their spectrum and power budget. The IMC best candidate is the final result of this more specific study.

The criteria posed to find our optimal mode cleaner candidate concern the suppression factors and the impinging intensity on the mirrors. The former are reported in eq. 8. They depend upon the finesse and the cavity layout. Our tests were carried out considering orders up to the 8-th one. The latter comes from the ideal intensity profile in eq. 1:

$$I_{max} = \frac{2GP_{in}}{\pi w_{in}^2} \quad (12)$$

where w_{in} is the beam width on the input mirror (equal to the one on the output one). The beam is always larger on the end mirror, producing a lower intensity peak. This value must not exceed the Laser-Induced Damage Threshold (LIDT), which is related to the substrate and coating material.

To make a conservative choice, we first selected RoC values ≥ 1 m, in order to broaden the beam

Table 1: SIPS mode cleaner parameters. They are compliant with all the requirements detailed in the text.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
L_{rt} [mm]	729.0	g_t	0.8784
L [mm]	364.5	TMS_s [MHz]	46.59
θ [deg]	2.0	TMS_t [MHz]	46.62
α [deg]	44.0	$ \Delta\Psi $ [mrad]	0.227
L_1 [mm]	352.2	π/\mathcal{F} [mrad]	31.0
L_2 [mm]	12.3	P_{st} [W]	129.1
h [mm]	352.0	P_{tr} [W]	3.874
RoC [m]	3.0	P_{end} [W]	0.125
R_1	0.970	w_0 [μm]	576.1
R_2	0.999	I_{max} [kW/cm^2]	24.77
\mathcal{F}	101.47	w_{in} [μm]	576.1
FSR [MHz]	411.2	$I_{max,in}$ [kW/cm^2]	24.76
FWHM [MHz]	4.053	w_{end} [μm]	614.6
g_s	0.8786	$I_{max,end}$ [kW/cm^2]	21.08

Figure 6: SIPS IMC normalized transmission spectrum for all the TEM_{nm} orders, with n even (solid lines) or odd (dashed lines). Tests are done up to the 8-th order: the closest lines to the main Gaussian resonance are the 4-th and 5-th order ones. The red dashed line marks the suppression threshold set at 20 dB.

size on the mirror. Further, only standard substrate values were tested, for easing the production process: $R_c \in [1; 1.5; 2; 3; 4]$ m. As a consequence, the round-trip length is also taken in the upper part of its interval: $L_{rt} \geq 500$ mm to avoid approaching instability, and to afford us a smaller θ . It was computed to be the smaller possible for each configuration, given a suitable space for the base mirrors to be effectively installed. Finally, mirrors power reflectivities are taken to be $R_1 = 0.970$ and $R_2 = 0.999$, so that the finesse is $\mathcal{F} = 101.5$. This choice allows to contain significantly the power lost

from the end mirror. Tests were repeated with more strict conditions on the distance of HOMs lines from the Gaussian one, keeping as last discriminating factor the intensity peak on the base mirrors, since it is always safely lower than the considered LIDT.

Table 1 lists all the characteristics of the SIPS IMC cavity chosen at the end of the selection process, and fig. 6 shows its transmission spectrum. The IMC best candidate has a round-trip length of $L_{rt} = 730$ mm and a RoC of the end mirror $R_c = 3.0$ m, so that $g = 0.88$. The very low value of $\theta = 2^\circ$ makes the astigmatism issue not relevant. Due to the symmetric configuration, the waist of the cavity eigenmode $w_0 = 576 \mu\text{m}$ falls at the middle point of the base side. $P_{st} = 129$ W, $P_{tr} = 3.87$ W are respectively the expected stored and transmitted power values, taken at resonance. The reflected beam power amounts to $P_{ref} = 1.04$ mW: this is enough for being detected by a suited photodiode, and applying the Pound-Drever-Hall locking technique. The two worst suppressed orders, as one can see from fig. 6, are the 4-th and the 5-th ones, with odd n . From eq. 8 it is possible to calculate $S_{13} = S_{31} = 19.6$ dB, and $S_{14} = S_{32} = S_{50} = 22.6$ dB. Other important S_{nm} values are the ones for the first two TEM _{nm} orders, since these arise in the propagating beam due to misalignments or mismatches with the Gaussian cavity eigenmode [18]. In our case, $S_{01} = 27.1$ dB and $S_{10} = 35.6$ dB for the first higher order modes. The second order suppression factors amount to $S_{02} = S_{20} = 32.5$ dB and $S_{11} = 33.8$ dB.

Mechanical tolerances

Every machining process is subject to mechanical tolerances for lengths and angles. For this reason, once the SIPS mode cleaner configuration was fixed, we concluded our analysis with simulations aimed at spotting the difference in the HOM detuning, due to a non perfect correspondence between the real cavity parameters and their ideal counterpart. This applies also to the end mirror RoC.

The contacted mechanical and optical producers guaranteed tolerances of 0.05 mm and 0.1° , respectively for lengths and angles, and a conservative error of $0.01 \times R_c = 0.03$ m on the end mirror RoC. These values were increased in our tests to 5 mm for the round-trip length, and 0.06 m concerning the RoC, in order to account also for assembling and installing errors.

As illustrated in fig. 6, the HOM lines closest to the Gaussian resonance are the 4th and 5th order ones, both with odd n index. These two detuning values in the ideal configuration can be computed from eq. 7 to be $|\Delta\nu_{13}| = 19.24$ MHz and $|\Delta\nu_{14}| = 27.35$ MHz. We report in fig. 7 the detuning of these two particular modes, which highlight a detuning variation approximately equal to 3 MHz. This brings to a suppression that in the worst case amounts to $S_{13} = 18.13$ dB and $S_{14} = 21.57$ dB.

Hence, this test did not arise possible alerts concerning the mechanical tolerances. However, we point out that a modulation frequency around 20 – 30 MHz should be avoided, in order for modulated signals from 4th and 5th order modes not to resonate with the fundamental mode. This contamination from sidebands could affect the quality of the Gaussian mode delivered by the cavity.

Conclusions

We presented the optical design process of a triangular mode cleaner cavity, suited for the small-scale suspended interferometer called SIPS. It will be employed as test bench for the expected broadband Quantum Noise reduction brought by the injection of EPR entangled squeezed vacuum states.

Figure 7: Tolerance tests performed on the 4th and 5th odd order, plotted as a function of the round-trip length and the RoC. The red rectangles mark the allowed ranges of variation for these two parameters within the chosen tolerances.

The mode cleaner presented here is compliant with all the investigated requirements: optical stability, low astigmatism, mode spacing, power and intensity thresholds, and of course mechanical feasibility and installation on the optical bench. The final choice fell on a configuration with a round-trip length of $L_{rt} = 730$ mm, and mirrors with power reflectivity equal to $R_1 = 0.970$ for the identical flat base mirrors, and $R_2 = 0.999$ for the curved end mirror found at the top of the triangle. The beam waist of the cavity eigenmode is equal to $w_0 = 576.1 \mu\text{m}$. The mode cleaner is currently undergoing the mechanical design process, before being manufactured in the next months.

A major advancing in the setup process will consist in the SIPS implementation next to the EPR optical bench, which will occur in the next future. Other experimental work of design, setup and characterization of some elements still missing in the optical lines is necessary to finally complete the construction of the EPR experiment.

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